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ANALYSIS OF THE POTENTIAL OF LEADING SECTORS AND THEIR CONTRIBUTION TO ECONOMIC GROWTH IN WEST LOMBOK REGENCY

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Abstract

The research method used in this study is LQ analysis to determine the base sector and non-base sector and shift share analysis to determine changes in regional economic structure/performance towards a higher economic structure (province) as a reference. This study uses secondary data obtained from the Central Statistics Agency. Based on the results of LQ's analysis, it is known that there are 12 base (superior) sectors in West Lombok Regency, namely a) the processing industry sector, b) the electricity and gas procurement sector, c) the water procurement sector, waste management, waste and recycling sector, d) the construction sector, e) the transportation and warehousing sector, f) the accommodation and food and beverage provision sector, g) the information and communication sector, h) Real Estate Sector, i) Government Administration, Defense and Compulsory Social Security Sector, j) Education Services Sector, k) Health Services and Social Activities Sector, l) Other Service Sectors. Based on the results of the shift share analysis, the national share/KPN value shows that the economy of West Lombok Regency is growing faster than the average growth of NTB Province. The proportional shift value / KPP shows positive and negative values, meaning that the sector's growth is slower than the same sector in NTB Province. The differential shift/KPPW value shows that West Lombok Regency has a low competitive advantage even though there are several sectors with positive values.

Key Words: leading sectors, economic growth

INTRODUCTION

Economic growth is one of the macroeconomic indicators used to measure economic performance in a region. This indicator helps identify sectors that contribute significantly to changes in regional economic growth. The rate of economic growth is calculated based on changes in GDP on the basis of constant prices in a given year compared to the previous year (Syahputra, 2017). To accelerate economic growth and increase its contribution to the total Gross Regional Domestic Product (GDP), the development of superior sectors can be used as a driving force for regional economic growth. Leading sectors are sectors that can encourage economic growth in their regions, including encouraging the growth of other economic sectors. The determination of the leading sector is based on the extent to which the sector contributes to the regional economy.

West Lombok Regency has a wealth of abundant natural resources and great potential if managed properly. The agricultural sector is one of the main sectors in this area which is the livelihood for most of the population. In addition, its natural resources also support the tourism sector which plays a role in contributing to the country's foreign exchange (Bappeda, 2020). The economic structure of West Lombok Regency is dominated by five categories of business sectors, namely: Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries, Wholesale and Retail Trade, Car and Motorcycle Repair, Construction, Transportation and Warehousing, and Accommodation and Food and Beverage Provision (Central Statistics Agency of West Lombok Regency, 2024)

Source: BPS Kabupaten Lombok Barat

In 2021, the GDP of West Lombok ADHK Regency reached 10.47 trillion rupiah, an increase from 10.12 trillion rupiah in 2020 with economic growth of 3.40 percent. This district has managed to recover from the impact of the pandemic supported by effective government policies and the positive impact of the implementation of WSBK and MotoGP which created around 6,900 jobs in six sectors, including construction, MSMEs, transportation, accommodation, food and drink, and tourism. GDP continues to increase until it reaches 11.38 trillion rupiah in 2023, up from 10.83 trillion rupiah in 2022, with economic growth of 5.03 percent (Central Statistics Agency of West Lombok Regency, 2024).

Source: BPS Kabupaten Lombok Barat

Over the past seven years, it has been seen that the economic growth rate of West Lombok Regency has experienced fluctuations and challenges due to earthquakes and pandemics. In 2018, West Lombok's economic growth slowed down to 0.57 percent due to the earthquake that hit Lombok Island. This resulted in the economic activities of the community being disrupted such as many business places were destroyed and damaged so that many people lost their jobs and many infrastructures such as public facilities, roads, bridges, schools and health facilities were severely damaged. In 2020, during the COVID-19 pandemic, the GDP growth rate dropped drastically to reach -7.03 percent due to the implementation of social distancing or restrictions on activities, which caused economic losses in West Lombok Regency due to reduced transaction activities. The implementation of social distancing has no effect on preventing the transmission of COVID-19. Therefore, the government has imposed PSBB (Large-Scale Social Restrictions) in several areas, including in West Lombok Regency. This resulted in many offices and some industries not operating, which ultimately caused economic losses (Central Statistics Agency of West Lombok Regency, 2022).

Based on constant price GDP, the economic growth of West Lombok Regency managed to record a positive growth of 3.40 percent. The increase in GDP is entirely due to an increase in production in all business sectors, without being affected by inflation. The year 2021 is a turning point which indicates that the economy of West Lombok Regency is starting to recover after previously experiencing a decline of 7.03 percent (Central Statistics Agency of West Lombok Regency, 2022).

The selection of superior sectors as the basis for regional development and cooperation between growth centers is one of the important efforts. The first step that must be taken is to identify sectors that have superiority, both in terms of supply, which is characterized by superior growth in technological aspects and socio-economic conditions of producers in the area. Therefore, an analysis is needed in the strategy of leading sectors that contribute significantly to regional economic growth in West Lombok Regency (bappenas, 2022). These superior sectors can be a priority in regional economic development planning. Therefore, development planning strategies are prepared based on the potential of each sector (Yusuf & Herlina, 2023). Related to what has been described earlier, this study aims to analyze the potential and contribution of leading sectors to economic growth in West Lombok Regency.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Economic Growth

According to Untoro (2010), economic growth is an increase in economic activity that results in an increase in the production of

goods and services and improves people's welfare in the long term. The capacity building is influenced or made possible by advances and adjustments in technology, institutions, and ideologies that adapt to existing demands. According to Mankiw (2016), the main factors that drive economic growth are the availability of various resources and increased efficiency in the use of production factors (Samuelson & Nordhaus, 2010). The process of economic growth is influenced by two types of factors, namely economic and non-economic factors. Economic growth in a country depends on natural resources, labor, capital, business, technology, and others. If economic growth is driven by an increase in the number of workers, this will not have an impact on increasing per capita income. However, when economic growth occurs due to the use of more productive resources, including labor, this will increase per capita income and improve people's living standards in general.

Gross Regional Domestic Product

GDP is the total net value of final goods and services produced by various economic sectors in a region in a certain period of time (Sasana, 2006). According to the Central Statistics Agency, GDP reflects a region's ability to manage existing natural resources. Therefore, the size of the GDP produced by each region is highly dependent on the potential production factors in the region. The limitation in the provision of production factors causes variations in the amount of GDP between regions. In a country's economy, every sector is interdependent on each other. They need support from other sectors, both in terms of raw materials and final products.

Export Base Theory

According to Sjafrizal (2018) this model was first introduced by Douglas C. North in 1955, based on the results of his research in several states of the United States. According to the model, the economic growth of a region is basically determined by the extent to which the region has a competitive advantage. If a region is able to encourage increased production in sectors that have competitive advantages as the basis for export activities, then the region's economic growth will experience a rapid increase. This can happen because the increase in export activities will produce a significant multiplier effect for the economy of the relevant region. In its application, base theory argues that the base sector plays a role as the main driver of economic change in a given region. In each region, there is a comparison of the number of workers in the base and non-base sectors that remains stable despite changes in the regional economic structure (Ananda, 2017).

Featured Sectors

According to Kuncoro (2013), the leading sector is a sector that has advantages both in terms of comparison and competitiveness compared to similar products from other regions and provides significant benefits. Leading sectors are usually related to a comparison, both regional, national and international scale. A sector can be said to be superior if it is able to compete with the same sector as other countries or regions. A region is said to have a superior sector if the area is able to compete with the same sector in other regions so that it is able to produce exports.

RESEARCH METHODS

Types of Research and Data Sources

This study uses a type of quantitative research with a descriptive approach. The type of data used is secondary data. The data used in the study is Gross Regional Domestic Product data obtained from the Central Statistics Agency of West Lombok Regency and the

Central Statistics Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province. The data used is data from West Lombok Regency.

Data Collection Methods

Data collection in this study uses documentation techniques and literature studies. Documentation is a method that involves collecting data derived from scientific publications such as journals, research reports, documents, archives, and relevant websites. The documents used are West Lombok Regency GDP data on the basis of constant prices by business field from 2017-2023 and West Nusa Tenggara Province GDP data for 2017-2023.

Data Analysis Procedure

1. Analysis of Location Quotient

The location quotient analysis technique is an indirect approach used to assess the performance of the economic base of a region. This method aims to identify economic sectors that are classified as superior sectors in the region.

$$LQ: \frac{Si/S}{Ni/N}$$

Information:

S_i : GDP sector i in West Lombok Regency

S : Total GDP in West Lombok Regency

N_i : GDP sector i in West Nusa Tenggara Province

N : Total GDP in West Nusa Tenggara Province

LQ value criteria are:

1. Value $LQ = 1$ shows that the growth rate of sector i in West Lombok Regency is comparable to the growth rate of the same sector in the economy of NTB Province.
2. Value $LQ > 1$ shows that the growth rate of sector i in West Lombok Regency is higher than the growth rate of the same sector in the economy of NTB Province.
3. Value $LQ < 1$ shows that the growth rate of sector i in West Lombok Regency is lower than the growth rate of the same sector in the economy of NTB Province.

2. Analysis of Shift Share

According to Tarigan (2005), shift share analysis can be used to compare sectoral growth between lower level administrative areas and higher administrative areas or what is often referred to as the national level. This study applies shift share analysis to understand changes in economic sectors in West Lombok Regency. The results of this analysis will show the performance of sectors in the Gross Regional Domestic Product of West Lombok Regency when compared to NTB Province.

$$\text{Shift Share: } (Nsi + Pr, i + Dr, i)$$

Where Nsi is National Share, Pr, i is Proportional Share and Dr, i is Differential Shift (Tarigan, 2005).

The components of shift share analysis consist of:

1. National Share

This component understands changes in the economic structure of a region that are affected by changes in the national economy. The results of the calculation will show the influence of national economic growth on regional economic development.

2. Proportional Shift

This component is to evaluate the impact of sector i nationally on the economic growth of sector i in West Lombok Regency. This measurement provides an opportunity for us to understand whether

the regional economy is focused on sectors that are growing faster than the economy used as a reference.

This component assesses the extent of the competitiveness of the local sector compared to the economic sector that is used as a reference.

3. Differential Shift

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

LQ Analysis Calculation

Business Field	LQ West Lombok Regency							Average	Information
	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023		
Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries	0.93	0.89	0.89	0.96	0.95	0.97	0.94	0.93	non-base
Mining and Quarrying	0.33	0.47	0.50	0.40	0.40	0.33	0.37	0.40	non-base
Processing Industry	1.13	1.03	1.04	1.13	1.12	1.16	1.13	1.11	base
Electricity and Gas Procurement	1.25	1.18	1.17	1.23	1.20	1.26	1.24	1.22	base
Water Procurement, Waste Management, Waste and Recycling	1.42	1.39	1.41	1.53	1.51	1.58	1.54	1.48	base
Construction	1.45	1.32	1.28	1.27	1.23	1.24	1.19	1.28	base
Wholesale and Retail Trade; Car and Motorcycle Repair	1.01	0.92	0.93	0.98	0.96	0.98	0.95	0.96	non-base
Transportation and Warehousing	1.47	1.43	1.43	1.87	2.01	2.07	2.00	1.75	base
Provision of Accommodation and Meals	3.85	3.47	3.39	3.22	3.19	3.30	3.20	3.37	base
Information and Communication	1.13	1.07	1.07	1.12	1.11	1.15	1.11	1.11	base
Financial Services and Insurance	0.95	0.89	0.89	1.00	1.01	1.02	1.04	0.97	non-base
Real Estate	1.16	1.03	1.03	1.10	1.09	1.13	1.09	1.09	base
Corporate Services	0.65	0.55	0.54	0.54	0.53	0.55	0.53	0.56	non-base
Government, Defense and Compulsory Social Security Administration	1.13	1.07	1.05	1.08	1.08	1.11	1.07	1.08	base
Educational Services	1.13	1.05	1.04	1.10	1.09	1.13	1.09	1.09	base
Health Services and Social Activities	1.03	0.96	0.96	1.07	1.06	1.08	1.04	1.03	base
Other Services	1.20	1.04	1.01	1.06	1.04	1.08	1.04	1.07	base

Source: processed data

Based on the table above, there are 12 leading sectors (bases) in West Lombok Regency, namely, Processing Industry, Electricity and Gas Procurement, Water Procurement, Waste Management, Waste and Recycling, Construction, Transportation and Warehousing, Accommodation and Food and Beverage Provision, Information and Communication, Real Estate, Government Administration, Defense and Compulsory Social Security, Education Services, Health Services and Social Activities, and Other Services. Thus, goods and services produced by superior sectors are able to support the needs of their own regions, including other regions. Meanwhile, there are 5 non-base (non-leading) sectors, namely Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries, Mining and Quarrying, Wholesale and Retail Trade; Car and Motorcycle Repair, Financial Services and Insurance, and Corporate Services.

Shift Share Analysis Calculation

Business Field	NS	PS	DS	EG
Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries	210,219.49	-25,543.59	-2,053.56	182,622.34
Mining and Quarrying	69,591.55	-120,684.66	88,760.07	37,666.95
Processing Industry	51,577.76	2,074.99	-6,021.94	47,630.81
Electricity and Gas Procurement	1,058.24	4,543.72	-202.09	5,399.86
Water Procurement, Waste Management, Waste and Recycling	1,116.91	131.75	958.14	2,206.80
Construction	142,334.60	105,052.00	-316,876.73	-69,490.13
Wholesale and Retail Trade; Car and Motorcycle Repair	133,213.71	160,691.63	-116,454.45	177,450.89

Transportation and Warehousing	101,432.36	-186,925.88	330,551.87	245,058.35
Provision of Accommodation and Meals	69,250.43	-112,503.57	-116,734.76	-159,987.90
Information and Communication	26,350.63	80,164.35	-7,456.85	99,058.12
Financial Services and Insurance	31,515.32	47,274.90	35,622.70	114,412.92
Real Estate	33,789.43	41,844.38	-30,477.98	45,155.83
Corporate Services	1,115.53	1,641.01	-2,695.83	60.71
Government, Defense and Compulsory Social Security Administration	56,683.49	16,953.13	-39,606.78	34,029.84
Educational Services	49,561.73	76,841.54	-23,066.66	103,336.61
Health Services and Social Activities	20,387.05	43,734.34	1,649.03	65,770.42
Other Services	26,046.37	37,881.42	-47,136.60	16,791.18
TOTAL	1,025,244.59	0.00	-78,071.00	947,173.59

Source: processed data

Based on the results of the shift share analysis in the table above, judging from the National Share/KPN in all economic sectors, it shows a positive value with a total output value of Rp.1,025,245 (in millions). The results show that the economy of West Lombok Regency is growing faster than the average growth of NTB Province. Based on the results of the analysis, the Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries sector is the sector with the fastest growth compared to other economic sectors, which is Rp.210,219 (in millions).

Based on the Proportional Shift/KPP, there are economic sectors with positive and negative values. Sectors with negative values are the Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries sector, the Mining and Quarrying sector, the Transportation and Warehousing sector, and the Accommodation and Food and Beverage Provision sector. This result shows that growth is slower than the same sector in NTB Province.

Based on the Differential Shift/KPPW value, there are several economic sectors with positive and negative values. Economic sectors with positive value are the Mining and Quarrying sector, the Water Procurement sector, Waste Management, Waste and Recycling, the Transportation and Warehousing sector, the Financial Services and Insurance sector and the Health Services and Social Activities sector. The results of the analysis show that the Transportation and Warehousing sector has the strongest competitiveness, which is Rp.330,552 (in millions). When viewed from the total value, negative values show that West Lombok Regency has a low competitive advantage even though there are several sectors with positive values. The total GDP growth value of West Lombok Regency has a positive value of Rp.947,174 (in millions), meaning that in West Lombok Regency there is an increase in regional economic performance.

DISCUSSION

To identify the potential of the economic sector in West Lombok Regency, an analysis was carried out on economic sectors that have superior potential. Here are the results of LQ analysis and Shift Share analysis:

No.	Business Field	Average	NS	PS	DS	EG
1	Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries	0.93	210,219	-25,544	-2054	182,622
2	Mining and Quarrying	0.40	69,592	-120,685	88,760	37,667
3	Processing Industry	1.11	51,578	2,075	-6,022	47,631
4	Electricity and Procurement	1.22	1,058	4,544	-202	5,400
5	Water Procurement, Waste Management, Waste and Recycling	1.48	1,117	132	958	2,207
6	Construction	1.28	142,335	105,052	-316,877	-69,490
7	Wholesale and Retail Trade; Car and Motorcycle Repair	0.96	133,214	160,692	-116,454	177,451
8	Transportation and Warehousing	1.75	101,432	-186,926	330,552	245,058
9	Provision of Accommodation and Meals	3.37	69,250	-112,504	-116,735	-159,988
10	Information and Communication	1.11	26,351	80,164	-7,457	99,058
11	Financial Services and Insurance	0.97	31,515	47,275	35,623	114,413
12	Real Estate	1.09	33,789	41,844	-30,478	45,156
13	Corporate Services	0.56	1,116	1,641	-2,696	61
14	Government, Defense and Compulsory Social Security Administration	1.08	56,683	16,953	-39,607	34,030

15	Educational Services	1.09	49,562	76,842	-23,067	103,337
16	Health Services and Social Activities	1.03	20,387	43,734	1,649	65,770
17	Other Services	1.07	26,046	37,881	-47,137	16,791
TOTAL			1025245	0	-78071	947173.6

Source: processed data

Based on the results of the calculation of all analysis tools, it can be concluded that:

1. Financial and Insurance Sector
Based on the average value of LQ < 1, NS (+), PS (+), and DS (+). This means that this sector has not been able to meet its own needs, the regional economy is concentrated in a sector that grows faster than the economy in the province because this sector has a competitive advantage.
2. Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries Sector
Based on the average value of LQ < 1, NS (+), PS (-), and DS (-). This means that this sector has not been able to meet its own needs and has become a sector with slower growth compared to the same sector in NTB Province. This is because this sector does not have a competitive advantage.
3. Mining and Quarrying Sector
Based on the average value of LQ < 1, NS (+), PS (-) and DS (+). This means that this sector has not been able to meet its own needs, the regional economy is concentrated by slower-growing sectors, but this sector has a competitive advantage.
4. Wholesale and Retail Trade Sector; Car and Motorcycle Repair, and Corporate Services Sector
Based on the average score of LQ < 1, NS (+), PS (+), and DS (-). This means that this sector has not been able to meet its own needs, the regional economy is concentrated by sectors that grow faster compared to the provincial economy, but this sector does not have a competitive advantage.
5. Water Procurement, Waste Management, Waste and Recycling, Health Services and Social Activities Sector
Based on the average value of LQ > 1, NS (+), PS (+) and DS (+). This means that this sector is able to meet its own needs and has the potential to be exported to other regions, the regional economy is concentrated in sectors that grow faster than the provincial economy because these sectors have a competitive advantage.
6. Processing Industry Sector, Electricity and Gas Procurement Sector, Construction Sector, Information and Communication Sector, Real Estate Sector, Government Administration Sector, Defense and Compulsory Social Security, Education Services Sector, and Other Service Sectors
Based on the average value of LQ > 1, NS (+), PS (+), and DS (-). This means that these sectors have been able to meet their own needs and have the possibility to be exported outside the region, regional growth is concentrated in sectors that grow faster than the provincial economy because these sectors do not have a competitive advantage.
7. Transportation and Warehousing Sector
Based on the average value of LQ > 1, NS (+), PS (-), DS (+). This means that this sector is able to meet its own needs and the possibility of being exported to other

regions, the regional economy is concentrated by slower growth sectors, but this sector has a competitive advantage.

8. Accommodation and Food & Beverage Provision Sector
Based on the average score of LQ > 1, KPN (+), KPP (-), KPPW (-). This means that this sector has been able to meet its own needs and the possibility of being exported to other regions, the regional economy is concentrated by slower growth sectors because this sector does not have a competitive advantage.

CONCLUSION

1. Based on LQ's analysis, there are 12 leading sectors in West Lombok Regency, namely a) Processing Industry Sector, b) Electricity and Gas Procurement Sector, c) Water Procurement Sector, Waste Management, Waste and Recycling, d) Construction Sector, e) Transportation and Warehousing Sector, f) Accommodation and Food and Beverage Provision Sector, g) Information and Communication Sector, h) Real Estate Sector, i) Government Administration, Defense and Compulsory Social Security Sectors, j) Education Services Sector, k) Health Services and Social Activities Sector, l) Other Service Sectors.
2. Based on the results of the shift share analysis, the national share value shows that the economy of West Lombok Regency is growing faster than the average growth of NTB Province. The proportional shift value shows positive and negative values, meaning that the sector's growth is slower than the same sector in NTB Province. The differential shift/KPPW value shows that West Lombok Regency has a low competitive advantage even though there are several sectors with positive values.

SUGGESTION

The government needs to take different steps to develop superior and non-superior sectors in order to boost the economy of West Lombok Regency. For the flagship sector, the main focus is to increase added value by utilizing modern technology, opening wider market access and providing incentives to local business actors. In addition, investment in infrastructure such as transportation, logistics and production facilities is essential to increase the competitiveness of the flagship sector. Meanwhile, non-superior sectors can be developed by finding untapped potential, providing skills training and creating more diverse products. With this approach, the superior sector can become the main driver of the economy while the non-superior sector becomes a buffer that strengthens economic stability in West Lombok Regency.

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